

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-2-174-IG-4% 40 rac	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	0722
Vial:	5	Acq. Method Set:	4%210400 40
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 2 174
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	300.0nm
Run Time:	11.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 300.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	7/23/2022 9:31:43 AM CST		
Date Processed:	3/9/2023 8:00:07 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	5.080	625474	13.98	89418
2	5.336	1591672	35.57	205465
3	5.772	1617565	36.15	198508
4	6.205	640305	14.31	74903

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-2-173-IG-4% 40 asy	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	0
Vial:	36	Acq. Method Set:	4%210400 40
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	2 173
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	300.0nm
Run Time:	10.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 300.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	6/27/2022 22:36:55 CST		
Date Processed:	7/4/2023 17:01:49 CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	5.330	37145	1.36	5100
2	5.620	2662850	97.68	328374
3	6.000	2010	0.07	403
4	6.354	24190	0.89	2730